

THE WAYS OF DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article analyzes the development of students' listening comprehension skills and also describes effective ways to develop learners' listening comprehension skills.

Keywords: listening, comprehension, skill, development, learner, effective ways, process, graphics.

Introduction. Teaching and learning foreign languages has become one of the requirements of time and space. After independence, Uzbekistan developed good conditions for studying foreign languages. "Currently, the teaching of foreign languages is given great importance in our country," declared our first president, Islam Karimov. This is not happening for no reason. Today, there is no need to overstate the importance of perfect knowledge of other languages for our nations, attempting to reclaim their place in the global community, and for our people, who are constructing a bright future in solidarity and collaboration with our international partners. As a logical continuation of these ideas, the President's Decision "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, can be cited as an example.

Currently, according to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev "On measures to bring the activity of popularizing the study of foreign languages to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated May 19, 2021, No. PQ-5117 By this, more attention is being paid to foreign languages.

Special attention is paid to the principle of four skills (reading, writing, listening, and speaking) in teaching and learning a foreign language. Therefore, it is important not to teach these four aspects at the same time, but to develop each of them separately. Below we will analyze the students' listening comprehension skills and effective ways to develop them.

In his 2009 article on developing listening skills, Wilmante Liubiniene stated the following. Developing listening skills in Wilmante Liubiniene is a complex process that is best developed with consistent practice, such as listening, reading, writing, and speaking. Listening is an important skill that is fundamental to successful communication and a successful professional career. Effective listening skills increase the ability to learn and adapt new information, knowledge, and skills.

"ESP: English for specific purposes" in the "Training And Development" training manual "Peace Corp Formation Collection & Exchange" mentioned their thoughts and used the following effective methods to effectively develop students' listening skills: Listening Comprehension, although important for English communication, is usually not given much attention as a language skill in English programs. As a native speaker, you have a unique advantage in developing listening comprehension skills in your students. Every word that is spoken in class can be useful in developing students' listening skills.

To be effective, your oral communication with the class must be understandable. Unintelligible speech is just "noise" and does not lead to language acquisition by students. Therefore, it is very important that you analyze the language level of your students and adjust your speech for their understanding. You should spend some time at the beginning of the course to make sure you understand. Your students may be used to hearing an English accent, for example, and it may take time for them to adjust to yours. Look closely at your students as you speak to gauge their understanding. Check comprehension frequently by asking questions or asking questions or comments about content that requires listening comprehension.

Writing exercises are a good way to test students' listening comprehension. Give them a short passage with a few words removed. Read the passage aloud twice. If they can't fill in the missing words, they won't understand the passage. Other ways to draw students' attention to these language structures include using cloze exercises, such as deleting articles or verbs if you are working on these forms.

A tape recorder is a valuable asset for a language teacher. If you have a tape recorder, you can pre-record the listening exercises so that you can walk around the classroom while the students do them. You can record other native English speakers reading crazy or other passages to help students practice listening to speakers with different accents and the opposite gender.

Give students practice taking notes while listening. Your students may be used to taking verbatim notes as dictation exercises and will need to practice listening for key information. Help them understand the meaning introduced by the speaker. A summary of such advice includes:

- a) Numerical sentences like "There are two reasons..."
- b) Rhetorical questions
- c) Introductory conclusions: "Let me first explain...The topic I want to discuss is interesting because..."
- d) "Another reason..."; develop an idea expressed by sentences like; "On the one hand... "; "Therefore..." and so on.
- e) "We focus on..." and others.
- f) "First..."; A chronology of ideas marked "Next"; "Finally,...";etc.
- g) Emphasis on ideas such as "This is important because..." "The important results were..." "Let me repeat..." etc.
- h) "In conclusion..." "As I have shown..."; a summary of the ideas expressed by etc.

Use a graphic whenever possible with listening exercises. Students may also need help learning to read graphics (maps, charts, etc.), as they may have little experience with this skill. Listening comprehension activities help them see how graphic information can be read and analyzed.

As we have seen, each method has its advantages. All of these approaches call for collaboration between the teacher and the student, as well as active participation by the student in the educational process.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the above methods develop the listening skills of learners. In addition, students and pupils should be directed to creativity, this will help them think logically in English, develop their worldviews, and their speech will become fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly will be formed.

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